

Assessing Health and Daily Activity Patterns in Elderly Populations: A Monitoring Study

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ABSTRACT

The increasing aging population necessitates continuous monitoring of daily activities to promote their well-being and independence. This study presents a sensor-based approach for monitoring the health and activity patterns of elderly individuals, focusing on specific activities such as combing hair, drinking from a glass, eating soup, and pouring water. By employing a combination of wearable and ambient sensors, the system effectively detects and analyzes movement patterns to identify potential health anomalies. The research was conducted with 16 participants from diverse age groups in a smart home environment, where their daily activities were recorded and analyzed. The result shows overall accuracy of 90.6% and demonstrates that subtle deviations in movement patterns can serve as early indicators of physical or cognitive decline. These findings highlight the potential of continuous activity monitoring to enhance elderly care by enabling timely interventions and providing valuable insights for caregivers and healthcare professionals.

KEYWORDS: *Wearable sensors, Activity detection, Elderly healthcare, Machine learning, Assisted living.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring daily activities like eating, drinking, walking, sitting, and other regular tasks is essential, particularly for the aged or disabled people, for several important reasons like health management, chronic disease monitoring, fall detection & prevention, safety and emergency response & real-time alerts etc. Changes in daily habits, such as reduced appetite, irregular eating patterns, or decreased mobility, can signal underlying health problems like malnutrition, dehydration, or the onset of chronic conditions. Many elderly and disabled individuals manage chronic diseases (e.g., diabetes, hypertension). Monitoring helps ensure compliance with treatment plans and provides data to adjust therapies as needed. Most importantly for those with mobility issues, monitoring walking and sitting activities can prevent falls and enable timely assistance if falls occur. Monitoring systems can send alerts if unusual patterns are detected, such as prolonged inactivity, missed meals, or difficulty moving, which may indicate an emergency.

Apart from these important issues, continuous monitoring may help to improve the issues like: quality of life, encouraging healthy habits, independence and autonomy peace of mind for caregivers, support for daily living etc. Regular monitoring allows family members and caregivers to ensure the well-being of their loved ones, even remotely. For individuals recovering from injuries or surgeries, tracking movement and activity helps measure progress and adapt rehabilitation programs. Monitoring can identify unhealthy routines (e.g., prolonged sitting or inadequate hydration) and promote healthier behaviours. Advanced monitoring systems allow aged or disabled individuals to live independently while still being under a safety net. Data collected can guide the design of personalized assistive devices or routines to enhance independence.

Periodically addressing small issues early, monitoring can prevent costly and avoidable hospital admissions. In summary, monitoring daily activities ensures physical safety, promotes health and well-being, and enables aged or disabled individuals to live with dignity and independence while supporting caregivers in delivering effective care.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have explored the use of sensor-based monitoring for elderly care. Wearable devices, such as accelerometers and gyroscopes, have been employed to track movement patterns and detect falls.

Ambient sensors embedded in smart home environments provide continuous monitoring without user intervention. Previous research has primarily focused on gross motor activities, such as walking, running and sitting; however, there is limited work on tracking fine motor activities such as eating or pouring liquids.

M. Farooq et al investigates wearable sensors for recognizing eating and drinking behaviours in naturalistic environments. Accelerometers and gyroscopes on the wrist capture movements associated with these activities, achieving high accuracy [1].

Discrete Human Activity Recognition and Fall Detection by Using Inertial Measurement Units and Radio Frequency Sensors proposed by Amin, M. G., et al [2]. It employs Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave (FMCW) RADAR and inertial measurement units to monitor activities like sitting, standing, and drinking. It is particularly useful for fall detection among the elderly. Deep learning models are used by Reyes-Ortiz, J. L., et al. [3] to classify activities such as walking, sitting, and drinking using sensor data from smartphones and smart watches. Human Activity Recognition in AAL Environments [4-6] uses classifier like Multi-Instance, random projections etc. and obtain good result. Li, F., et al explores deep learning models' ability to detect subtle activities like drinking and reading, highlighting current limitations and areas for improvement [8].

These studies collectively demonstrate advancements in human activity recognition, utilizing various sensors and machine learning techniques to detect daily activities.

This study builds upon existing research by integrating multiple sensor types to enhance the accuracy of activity recognition. By employing machine learning algorithms to analyze collected data, we aim to develop a robust system capable of detecting minor deviations in daily activities that may indicate health deterioration.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study involved a group of 16 individuals aged between 19 to 81 years. Participants performed the four selected activities in a controlled environment while being monitored using a combination of technologies. The methodology was designed to ensure high accuracy in data collection, processing and interpretation and the block diagram is represented in the Figure1.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the activity detection.

Here the following components were utilized:

Choice of Activities: The study solely focuses on four daily activities, combing hair, drinking from a glass, pouring water and eating soup that are necessary in taking care of oneself and commonly occur in real daily livings along with walking, running, sitting etc.

Data Collection: This study uses benchmark human motion primitive data set (HMP) [9]. The Dataset is composed of the recordings of 14 simple activities of daily living (brush_teeth, climb_stairs, comb_hair, descend_stairs, drink_glass, eat_meat, eat_soup, getup_bed, liedown_bed, pour_water, sitdown_chair, standup_chair, use_telephone, walk) performed by a total of 16 volunteers wearing a tri axial accelerometer on the right wrist out of which four very common activities: comb_hair, eat_soup, drink_glass and pour_water are considered for this study. The raw sensor data were cleaned to remove noise and irrelevant fluctuations. The X, Y and Z axial acceleration data plot with respect to time is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Plot of tri-axial acceleration data for four daily activities

Feature extraction: The dataset contains acceleration data of three axis marked as X, Y and Z.

Magnitude of a sample is calculated using the formula:

$$M = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2}$$

Then five statistical time domain features such as mean, variance, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis are extracted from the signal and the X, Y and Z directional data separately. This gives rise to a 20 dimensional feature set.

Classification: The scatter plots of various combinations of the features are done to visually test the ability of these features to classify the activities. The findings of this test are pointed in results section. Being assured with the ability of the feature set classifier models are developed using different machine learning algorithms. Among them Linear Support Vector Machine (L-SVM), Quadratic Support Vector Machine (Q-SVM) and Bagged trees gave significant classification accuracy.

This daily activity classification method ensured that the collected data was comprehensive, leading to reliable and interpretable results in assessing elderly activity patterns.

4. RESULTS

In this work simple statistical features from tri-axial accelerometer data are extracted to conduct activity classification. The 2D scatter plots of different combinations of features shows a good clustering for different types of ADLs. Two such plots are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of (a) Mean Magnitude Vs Skewness of X data, (b) Mean of Y data Vs Variance of Z data

Notable findings from scatter plots include:

1. Combing Hair: Mean magnitude was found to be very low indicating less movement while doing the activity.
2. Drinking from a glass: Mean magnitude was high with moderate standard deviation indicating a reasonable amount of variability in the movement.
3. Pouring Water: Mean magnitude was high with high standard deviation indicating a significant amount of variability in the movement.
4. Eating soup: Standard deviation was low indicating very less movement while doing the activity compared to others.

The extracted feature set was tested using different machine learning algorithms. Three of them snowed satisfactory result. These are Linear Support Vector Machine (L-SVM), Quadratic Support Vector Machine (Q-SVM) and Bagged trees ensemble learning method. The Bagged trees classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 90.6% in classifying the four activities. The confusion matrix of all the three classifiers are shown in Figure 4. The Four classified activities combing hair, drinking from a glass, eating soup and pouring water are denoted as 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively in the figure.

Figure 4. Confusion matrix of (a) Linear SVM, (b) Quadratic SVM, (c) Bagged Trees Classifier

The performances of these three classifiers are further analyzed by calculating two metrics: Accuracy and F1 score. These are summarised in table 1. It is seen that the Accuracy and F1 both for Comb hair are 100% for all the classifiers which is evident from the scatter plots of different features. The accuracy of the detection of the drink from glass activity is very poor for L-SVM as 15 samples of this class are wrongly classified as Eat soup causing a reduction in overall accuracy of this classifier. While the other two classifiers secure an overall accuracy above 90% maintaining F1 score for all the individual classes more than 0.85. The results obtained from these three classification models are satisfactory and comparable with other state of the art works. A comparison with few other HAR systems is shown in table 2. In all of the works the accuracy ranges between 85 to 95% where multiple body worn sensors are used, whereas this method uses only one tri-axial accelerometer. The performance of this method is even comparable with image-based LSTM model [12] for HAR. This ensures a strong applicability of the statistical feature analysis of Accelerometer data in detection of ADLs.

Table 1. Performance metrics of three classifiers.

Classifier Activity	L-SVM		Q-SVM		Bagged Trees	
	Accuracy	F1	Accuracy	F1	Accuracy	F1
Comb hair	1	1	1	1	1	1
Drink from glass	0.73	0.8	0.83	0.87	0.83	0.87
Eat soup	0.93	0.83	0.93	0.86	0.93	0.89
Pour water	0.85	0.87	0.92	0.89	0.88	0.87
Overall	0.875	-	0.903	-	0.906	-

Table 2. Comparison with existing works.

Sl. No.	Author	Activity	Used sensors	Accuracy
1	Lester, Jonathon and Choudhury, Tanzeem and Borriello, Gaetano[10]	Riding elevator down, Riding elevator up, Standing, Brushing Teeth	ARM7-based wireless sensor node	90%
2.	Fridriksdottir, E, Bonomi, A.G. [11]	lying in bed, upright posture, walking, wheelchair transport, stair ascent and stair descent	Tri-axial accelerometer	94.52%
3.	Guerra, B.M.V. et al. [12]	standing, sitting, lying, dangerous sitting and transition	Camera	85.7%
4.	Zhou, F. et al. [13]	sit, stand, go slow, go fast, upstairs, downstairs, jog and run fast	Multiple body worn and ambient object mounted IMU and proximity sensors	85.3 %
5.	Hsu, Y. -L. [14]	walk, run, upstairs, downstairs, stand up and squat, drink, take elevator, still, sit, and lie	Tri-axial accelerometer, tri-axial gyroscope	90.5%

6.	Proposed Work	combing hair, drinking from a glass, eating soup, and pouring water	Tri-axial accelerometer	90.6%
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5. CONCLUSIONS

This research highlights the effectiveness of smart monitoring systems in accurately tracking the daily activities of elderly individuals. By analyzing variations in activity performance—such as slower movements or irregular motion patterns—potential health concerns can be identified early, enabling timely interventions. The proposed system offers a cost-effective and non-intrusive solution by utilizing data from a wrist-worn accelerometer. With over 90% accuracy, the model effectively detects daily activities using classical machine learning algorithms and simple time-domain statistical features, ensuring low computational complexity.

Future work will focus on expanding the system's capabilities by detecting a broader range of activities of daily living (ADLs), enhancing real-time analysis, and integrating the solution into smart home environments. This integration aims to promote independent aging by providing continuous, proactive healthcare monitoring, ultimately improving the quality of life for elderly individuals

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